

Clinico-Histopathological Study of Leprosy in a Medical College and Hospital in Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract:

Introduction: Leprosy also known as Hansen's disease is one of the oldest diseases known to mankind. It is a chronic infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*. It still remains as a major public health problem facing India. Nearly, 52% of all world leprosy cases are reported from India. The spectrum of presentation of leprosy is very wide. Histopathology is an important tool in making a definitive diagnosis.

Aim: To study the clinicopathological spectrum of leprosy in a Medical College Hospital in Banthra, Shahjahanpur, Uttar Pradesh.

Materials and Methods: A prospective hospital-based study of clinically diagnosed Hansen's disease [leprosy] cases was conducted over a period of 13 months from March 2023 to March 2024 comprising of 209 cases. Lesional skin biopsies obtained were formalin fixed, processed and stained with Haematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) followed by Wade-fite staining. The lesions were classified on microscopy as per Ridley-Jopling classification.

Results: A total of 209 cases were studied. Highest incidence was in the age group of 21 to 30 years for both males and females. Males were more affected (M:F=3.4:1). Most common clinical feature was loss of sensation. The commonest reported histopathological type was borderline tuberculoid (33.3%) followed by lepromatous leprosy (43%). Overall Wade-fite staining was positive in 62 (29.9%) cases.

Conclusion: The spectrum of presentation of leprosy is very wide and there is clinical overlap between different types of leprosy. Histopathology still remains the gold standard for early diagnosis and classification of the disease. Accurate diagnosis forms the backbone for appropriate treatment and preventing deformities and drug resistance.

Keywords: Histopathology, Leprosy, Skin biopsies.

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Introduction

Leprosy is one of the oldest diseases known to man. It is a chronic infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium leprae* (*M. leprae*). Hansen's disease was discovered by Sir Gerhard Armauer Hansen in 1873 [1]. Although, leprosy had already been described in Susruth Samhita (600 BC) [2]. It is a granulomatous disease primarily affecting the skin and peripheral nerves. It can also involve muscles, eyes, bone, testis and internal organs to a varying extent [3]. Clinically and histopathologically presentation of leprosy depends

on the host cellular immune response [4]. The diagnosis depends on microscopy and demonstration of Acid-Fast Bacilli (*lepra bacilli*) on tissue biopsy [5,6]. With developed programmes and unified approach there have been substantial reduction in the disease burden but leprosy is still one of the major public health problem in India. National Leprosy Eradication Programme (NLEP) has been successful in achieving the target of eliminating leprosy {Prevalence Rate (PR) of <1/10000 population} from India in January 2006.

[7] Despite this, India still alone accounts for nearly 52% of the world leprosy cases [8]. The scenario in Uttar Pradesh [U.P.] is far from rosy and the state is still a hotspot for leprosy. The Annual New Case Detection Rate (ANCDR) is 4.56/10,000 population in Shahjahanpur district in U.P where our study has been done; being an endemic area for leprosy. In the absence of treatment leprosy tends to be progressive and can cause permanent damage to skin, nerves, limbs and eyes. leading to disfigurement. Hence, histopathological examination remains a cornerstone in the diagnosis and appropriate management of this disease.

Materials and Methods:

A prospective hospital-based study was conducted in Department of Dermatology and Pathology, Varun Arjun Medical College, Banthra, Shahjahanpur over a period of 13 months (March 2023 to March 2024). 209 patients clinically diagnosed of Hansen’s disease [leprosy] of all age groups and both sexes were included. A 3 mm lesional skin punch biopsies were obtained by dermatologists. These biopsies were formalin-

fixed, routinely processed and stained with H&E followed by Wade- Fite staining. The lesions were graded as per the Ridley-Jopling classification into tuberculoid leprosy, borderline tuberculoid, borderline, borderline lepromatous and lepromatous leprosy, Type I, Type II Lepre reactions, Histoid and Indeterminate variants were also included in the study. Only new/fresh cases were included in the study. Relapsed, follow-up cases were exempted from our study.

Results:

A total of 209 cases were studied. Male: Female ratio-3.4:1(Figure1). Highest incidence of leprosy was noted in the age group of 21-30 years. On histopathology, Borderline Tuberculoid category was the most frequently reported with 33.33% of cases followed by lepromatous leprosy (20.7%). [Figure2]. Two cases were diagnosed as non-specific dermatitis. Clinico-pathologic concordance was most seen in HL followed by BL and LL. Two cases which were diagnosed as Hansen’s clinically were seen to be non-specific dermatitis histologically.

Figure 1: Gender distribution of leprosy cases

Figure 2: Distribution of leprosy cases in males and females

Table 1: Distribution of leprosy cases according to age group

Age Group	1-10	11-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	61-70	71-80	Total
TL	0	0	3	1	2	0	0	1	7
BT	1	2	18	14	15	11	6	2	69
BB	0	1	7	4	10	1	3	2	28
BL	1	0	11	5	8	2	0	1	29
LL	0	1	18	2	16	1	3	2	43
Type I Reaction	1	0	0	1	0	2	3	1	08
ENL	0	0	2	8	4	0	3	1	18
HL	0	0	0	0	0	0	01	0	01
IL	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	04

Table 2: Distribution of Wade-fite positive cases among different histopathological types

Type	Total cases	Positivity	Percentage[%]
TL	7	M=0,F=0	0%
BT	69	M=0,F=0	0%
BB	28	M=0,F=0	0%
BL	29	8[M=07,F=01]	29.8%
LL	43	43[M=40,F=03]	100%
Type I reaction	08	02[M=2,F=0]	25%
ENL	18	09[M=07,F=02]	52.1%
HL	01	M=0,F=0	0%
IL	04	M=0,F=0	0%

TT: Tuberculoid Leprosy, BT: Borderline Tuberculoid Leprosy, BB: Borderline Borderline Leprosy, BL: Boderline lepromatous Leprosy, LL: Lepromatous Leprosy, Type I lepra reaction: Upgrading or Downgrading reaction, ENL [Type II lepra reaction]: Eyrethema Nodosum Leprosus, HL: Histoid Leprosy, IL: Indeterminate Leprosy

Table3: Correlation between clinical and histopathological classification of leprosy Clinical & Histopathological Correlation

Histo diagnosis	Clinical Diagnosis									% concordance
	TT	BT	BB	BL	LL	BTwTyI	ENL	HL	IL	
TT[7]	5	2								71.4
BT[69]	3	58	1	6	1					84
BB[28]		1	24	2	1					85.7
BL[29]				27	2					93
LL[43]				4	39					90.6
BTwType I		2	1			5				62.5
ENL					2		16			88.8
HL								1		100
IL			2	1					1	25
Non-specific dermatitis		2								0

Tuberculoid Leprosy: The patients of TT were diagnosed clinically by the presence of asymmetrical, large hypopigmented, hypoanesthetic patches. Anesthesia present, Nerves – Thickened presence of feeding nerves, no systemic involvement, Sweating – lost, Skin smear – Negative, Lepromin tests – Strongly positive.

Figure 3

Figure 4: Tuberculoid leprosy (H&E, 10x with well-formed granulomas)

Borderline Tuberculoid: Few (upto 10) asymmetric large , hypopigmented / skin Colored macules plaques with ill-defined margins with presence of satellite lesions near advancing margin of patch, marked anesthesia , irregular / asymmetrical nerve involvement , no systemic involvement , skin smears negative, lepromin test weakly positive .

Figure 5

Figure 6: Borderline Tuberculoid Leprosy with poorly formed granulomas, giant cells. (H & E;40x)

Mid-Borderline Leprosy: Unstable form , multiple symmetrical lesions ranging from papules, macules and plaque. Plaques shows well demarcated edges with punched out center with moderate anesthesia, variable nerve involvement , Skin smear positive , lepromin test negative .

Figure 7

Figure 8: Borderline Borderline Leprosy showing intercellular edema.(H & E;40x)

Borderline Lepromatous Leprosy: Multiple almost symmetrical lesions, start as macule later becomes infiltrated centrally form papules, nodules and plaques with sloping edges. Glove & stocking hypoesthesia occurs later, widespread nerve involvement, skin smear positive, lepromin test negative.

Figure 9

Figure 10: Borderline Lepromatous Leprosy shows thinning of epidermis and flattening of rete ridges. (H & E;40x)

Lepromatous Leprosy: Numerous lesions, glove and stocking anesthesia, dry skin ichthyosis present, skin smears always positive, mucosal & systemic involvement present.

Figure 11

Figure 12: Lepromatous leprosy (H&E; 40x) with diffuse sheets of Virchow cells

Figure 13: Lepromatous leprosy show lepra bacilli in globi arrangement (Wade-fite stain;100x)

Figure 14: Indeterminate Leprosy, with scant perivascular lymphocytic infiltrate [H&E, 40x]

Histoid Leprosy:

Figure 15

Figure 16: Histoid leprosy (hematoxylin and eosin stain $\times 40$) showing storiform pattern of spindle shaped macrophages

Discussion:

Leprosy is a chronic granulomatous disease caused due to infection by *M. leprae*. Depending upon the immune status of the host; leprosy can have varied clinic-pathological presentations. Accurate diagnosis and classification are important for correct timely treatment, management and prevention of disabilities.

There are various classification systems like India, Madrid, Ridley Jopling classification, etc., The most widely used Ridley-Jopling classification is based on clinical, bacteriological, pathological and immunological parameters [12]. Indeterminate and histoid subtypes of leprosy were also included in present study.

Histopathological examination of skin lesions remains the gold standard for diagnosis [13]. The findings used for microscopic diagnosis are involvement of sub-epidermal zone, granuloma formation, density of lymphocytic infiltrate, nerve involvement, presence of *M. leprae* and epithelioid cells and other cellular elements in biopsy sections [14]

Leprosy can occur at all ages [15]. In the present study majority of the cases belonged to 21-30 years age group. This is in similarity to other published Indian studies which found most of the cases in 21-40 age groups [16-23]. This is a cause for concern since this is the prime productive age and has economic implications for the nation. In the present study males were more affected than female. Other studies too have reported a male preponderance [Fig-1] [16-23]. The most common type of leprosy in the present study was BT (33.3%), followed by LL (20.7%), BL (14%), BB(13.5%) ENL (8.69%), Type I reaction (3.86%), TT (3.3%) IL (1.93%), HL (0.48%) [Fig-2]. The borderline group constituted the major spectrum (63.8%) of the disorder which includes BT, BB and BL and BT with type I lepra reaction. High bacteriological index was seen in LL type similar to studies by Chintal et al and Anush et al [21,22]

IL is an early and transitory stage of leprosy found in persons, whose immunological status is yet to be determined and it may progress to one of the other determinate forms of the disease. The IL type appears to be problematic due to non-specific histology of the lesion. The diagnosis of IL also depends on many factors such as nature and depth of biopsy, the quality of sections and the number of sections examined both H&E and acid fast stained.

There are divergent reports regarding the common subtype of leprosy. Similar findings have been reported by other published Indian papers [13,18-20,22,23]. Contrary to present findings, study conducted by Kaur I et al., observed LL type [Table/Fig-7] to be the commonest type in their

series [17] while, Mathur MC et al., found TT to be the most common type [24]. Other set of studies have reported BT as the most frequent histopathological type [25-27]. Similar to our studies, This variation could be due to the regional differences, socioeconomic and immune status of the study population [18]. With treatment, borderline group move towards tuberculoid pole and with delayed treatment, it moves towards lepromatous pole [28]. Clinicopathological concordance in our study was seen in 70.1% cases in contrast to Singh et al where 93.69% cases showed concordance and study by Bhatia et al showed 95% concordance [19,20]

Various factors influence histopathological diagnosis of leprosy including the size of specimen, biopsy site and depth of biopsy, age of lesion, immunological status of patient and treatment history [23]. Serial biopsies from same lesion or from paired lesion help in understanding the disease better [22]. Classification of leprosy cases into paucibacillary and multibacillary variants is important for multidrug treatment. WHO study group (1982) included IL, TT, BT in the paucibacillary spectrum while BB, BL, LL were classified as multibacillary to prevent drug resistance [29]. However, in 1988 WHO expert committee made modification to include only smear negative IL, TT, BT cases in paucibacillary group and any case belonging to these types with smear positivity are to be typed as multibacillary [30]. Diagnosis of leprosy must be a multidisciplinary effort of the dermatologist, and pathologist .in endemic areas of leprosy any atypical rash may be over diagnosed as leprosy more so because paucibacillary types do not show bacilli on slit skin smears; as in our study wherein two cases were diagnosed as Hansen's Disease, BT but histologically were found to be non-specific dermatitis.[22]

Conclusion:

The spectrum of leprosy presentation is very wide. Diagnosing this disease is a challenge. Histopathology plays an important role in making definite diagnosis. It still remains the gold standard for early diagnosis and classification of leprosy. Leprosy is curable with multidrug therapy. Accurate diagnosis is required for proper treatment, preventing deformities and drug resistance. Histopathology, also useful for monitoring treatment response. In the present study, the most common affected age group was 21-30 years with male predominance .This is a cause for concern as this is the economically productive group. The predominance of borderline spectrum and multibacillary leprosy could be due to lower socioeconomic status, poor sanitary conditions, overcrowding and illiteracy in the region.

Correlation of clinical and histopathological features along with bacteriological index is more useful for accurate typing of leprosy than considering a single parameter alone as there is some degree of overlap between the different types of leprosy. This helps clinicians for better care and management of disease and thus to decrease the burden of the disease in society, The findings of this study might help state and centre policy makers to develop more effective strategies for truly achieving the target of eradicating leprosy.

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